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EFFECTIVENESS OF MODELING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the educational policy in our Republic is not only national interests, but global development, which affects the education system, formed social competence is the goal of any educational program, the basis of socialization.

Keywords: Independence, goal orientation, responsibility, creativity, advanced idea, modeling.

To this day, the freedom of individuality and self-expression manifestation of the decisive principle of education in the educational system - the individual is gaining importance in education. In modern society, there is a new understanding of the functional purpose of professional education, its educational component, because professional education responds as a social institution, the content of its socio-pedagogical functions in society requires updating in order to develop the individual's personal potential. From the point of view of the newly emerging socio-cultural paradigm, the person as a capable active subject is aimed at showing creativity in various spheres of activity. On the way to the development of the new Uzbekistan, today's higher education institutions, which have new goals and tasks set by the state, are in this direction, that is, in changing the socio-pedagogical tasks of higher educational institutions and higher invited to become a leader in the distribution of the best, advanced innovative pedagogical technologies aimed at solving a number of important socio-economic problems, which help to rapidly develop the professional system of education.

In modern conditions, higher education institutions are acquiring new functions and renewing existing traditional functions. We need to understand the new socio-pedagogical function of the professional education system in providing modern pedagogical knowledge. It leads to a serious renewal of the role and importance of professional education in today's Uzbek society. This will be strengthened by the conditions of integration of Uzbekistan into the world economic and educational community. The socio-pedagogical function of higher educational institutions is to fundamentally change the role of higher

educational institutions in society, to educate a modern specialist in the conditions of socio-cultural changes conditioned by the influence of socio-economic development factors. Reconceptualization of educational activity in higher educational institutions from the point of view of the function of educating a modern competitive specialist is possible only with the position of an interdisciplinary approach, which is consistent between pedagogy and other branches of science in order to develop and update conceptual ideas about educating young students. justifies the need for communication.

At present, the process of continuous interaction of the state, society, employers and educational institutions is taking place during the implementation of the socio-pedagogical function by higher educational institutions. The purpose of improving the social competence of students is to emphasize the individual's self-education and self-formation, the objective shift to the manifestation of subjective qualities. Based on scientific-practical modeling and the implementation of educational strategies in higher educational institutions, the educational activities that dynamically shape the educational environment and at the same time are formed by it are carried out in the specially structured educational system of the higher educational institution. implies the implementation of a significant socio-pedagogical function.

Students' awareness of social reality, readiness for leadership and the ability to communicate with other people, make responsible decisions in the educational process, comply with certain regulatory requirements of their field, the ability to know innovative educational technologies, have important methods of social activity to be To be able to use one's capabilities at a high level and to achieve socially significant innovative cooperation: to realize internal free movement based on "existential motives".

Formed social competence is the goal of any educational program, the basis of socialization. Social competence gives a person the ability to analyze the daily situation, predict its development, plan different behaviors of other people, cooperate on the basis of collected and processed social information, act independently and responsibly. The process of forming social competence should take into account the specific characteristics of the real life conditions of a modern person, because today a person has a wide range of social relations and connections, performs complex social actions, which must be mastered by a person during the period of growth.

The need to be based on the following components in the development of students' social activity was embedded in the content of the chapter: a high level of self-awareness; citizenship, self-esteem, self-respect, discipline, correctness; attention to spiritual values; to feel independence and responsibility in making decisions; freely choose the content of life activities; kindness, goodness; altruism, patience, endurance, humility; striving to understand peace, good neighborliness, national and universal values; the need for knowledge and self-awareness, beauty, reflection, communication and deep understanding of the meaning of life; autonomy of the inner world, integrity; advanced skills; need for activity-changing scientific knowledge, qualifications, skills, intellect, institution, creative life; know the basics of economics; diligence, thrift; learning foreign languages; knowledge of national and religious traditions; healthy lifestyle; physical fitness; aesthetic taste, good deeds; cleanliness, improvement of the environment and ensuring family well-being; erudition, competence; entrepreneurship, competitiveness, management ability; accessibility; ability of creative professional thinking, knowledge of history, culture of different peoples, etc.

The essence of social competence of students includes the following; a person's awareness of social reality, readiness for leadership and the ability to communicate with other people, making responsible decisions in life situations, compliance with certain normative requirements of society, the ability to foresee the consequences for oneself and others, has important methods of life activity to be Features of

this; include efficiency, current and historical qualities. This includes a real "Intrinsic Value" (subculture) influence.

Answering the question of what kind of student is needed today or tomorrow, with the help of the model, we get a scientifically based description of the professional person. This makes it possible to move away from randomness and subjectivity in setting the educational goal, because the vision of the modern ideal specialist models the goal of his education.

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